

FUNCTIONALIZED CELLULOSE: FROM THEORY TO CONCRETE APPLICATIONS

Belgacem N., Bras J.

Univ. Grenoble Alpes, CNRS, Grenoble INP (Institute of Engineering Univ. Grenoble Alpes), LGP2, Grenoble, France

The present lecture is focused on the recent advances on cellulose (from macromolecular size to fibers morphologies) and its chemical modification (mainly surface modification), as a starting material for medical applications. It will be divided into three parts:

1. The first part will be devoted to the basic consideration on cellulose, its origin and current and perspective uses with a special focus on those aiming at helping medicine in specific challenges.
2. Then, surface phenomena with a special care about the difficulties associated with surface contamination, the surface energy characterization, the surface properties determinations, will be given, with a focus on the potentiality of providing high-added value functions to these natural renewable resources [1, 2].
3. The third part points out the most relevant surface modification strategies to which the cellulose surface could be subjected, in order to graft new functions. These include, (i) physical treatments (ii) chemical grafting by direct condensation, “grafting from” and “grafting onto” approaches. In this context, recent works investigating green solvent-based or solvent-less systems will be reported [1, 2].
4. All these treatments aim at providing these substrates specific functions, such as hydrophobic character, anti-microbial properties, etc. [1, 2]. Typical examples of achievements in this field will be given and discussed, with a special focus on those aiming at helping medicine in specific challenges. Thus, active surfaces (antimicrobial for example) working in contact or release modes will be given. Other energy providing cellulose-based medical devices will also be described and discussed.

Finally, some relevant concluding remarks and perspectives will be given.

REFERENCES

1. Rol F., M. N. Belgacem M. N., Gandini A., Bras J. Recent advances in surface-modified cellulose nanofibrils. *Progress in Polymer Science*, 88 (2019) 241–264
2. A. Gandini, Belgacem M. N. The surface and in-depth modification of cellulose fibers. *Advances in Polymer Science*, 271 (2016) 169-206.